

Welcome to the DATAMITE Newsletter

Our motto: Unleashing the Monetisation Potential of Data.
How will **DATAMITE** benefit society? Who is behind the project? Enjoy
your reading.

The banner has a blue-to-orange gradient top section. On the left, there is a circular image showing a globe with a bar chart overlaid on it. The Datamite logo and 'datamite' text are on the left side of the top section. On the right side of the top section, there is a small European Union flag icon followed by the text 'Funded by the European Union'. Below the top section, the word 'Article' is written in orange, followed by the article title 'The state of data monetization in the EU: How DATAMITE will contribute to unlock the potential of data' in white text on a dark blue background.

datamite

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Article

The state of data
monetization in the EU: How
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How DATAMITE will contribute to unlock the potential of data

In an increasingly data-driven world, organisations are realising the immense potential of data monetization. By harnessing the power of data, businesses can gain valuable insights, make informed decisions, and even create new revenue streams. DATAMITE is designed to revolutionise the European data market by helping users who want to better monetise their data and become the leading edge of the data monetisation.

[Learn how](#)

Deliverable 6.1 Impact Master Plan, now available

Impact Master Plan, now available

The **DATAMITE Deliverable 6.1 - Impact Master plan, is now available in Zenodo** for the public to read and download. This document provides a detailed overview of DATAMITE's strategy, defining the goals, priorities and potential implementation mechanisms to achieve all planned outcomes.

[Read & download it](#)

Introducing one of DATAMITE's use cases
**Corporate Multi-Site
Data Exchange**

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Use Case: Corporate Multi-Site Data Exchange

To be able to measure the value offered by the **DATAMITE framework it is ideal to be tested over an actual use case** that combines data from different data platforms and systems and has real business value for the organisation. **OTE**, the largest mobile network operator in Greece, **fulfils all the necessary requirements** to be one of the Use Cases of the project.

[Call to action](#)

DATAMITE host its second plenary meeting in Athens

From 28 to 30 June, the **DATAMITE Consortium met** at the premises of [OTE Group of Companies](#) in Athens **to host its second plenary meeting**. Three days of intense work that have served to recognise what has been achieved so far and to focus on the road ahead to achieve our goal.

[Discover more](#)

Participation in international events and conferences

DATAMITE participates in EGI2023

EGI2023 took place from 19 to 23 June. **DATAMITE has been one of the European projects represented**, both with a physical booth and with the intervention of some of the members of the consortium in different sessions

[Discover more](#)

DATAMITE at DATA WEEK

The **Data Week 2023** took place from 13 to 19 June 2023. Liliana Beltrán, Project Manager at [ITI](#), representing **DATAMITE participated** in the session on

“Technological Enablers for the Next-Level Data Economy”.

[Learn more](#)

National Field Days (Poland)

Two members of the DATAMITE consortium had a leading role during the event.

[Read it](#)

Women in Tech Summit 2023

DATAMITE joined the Perspektywy Women In Tech Summit on the PSNC booth.

[Read it](#)

ITM Industry Europe 2023

ITM Industry Europe is the leading trade fair in Poland. DATAMITE was there.

[Read it](#)

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